

Engaging the Classroom – ATLAS Visits, Virtual Visits, Masterclasses, Cheat Sheets and More

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17-21 July 2023

Abstract

The ATLAS Collaboration provides a range of outreach and engagement opportunities appropriate for classroom engagement with particle physics developed by the ATLAS Collaboration. Here we present details of the exhibits/features and use of the new ATLAS Visitors Centre at CERN – the most visited external visitor site at CERN – as well as an overview of the highly-successful Virtual Visit programme bringing CERN and the ATLAS experiment to tens of thousands of people. We also present an overview of ATLAS contributions to International Masterclasses and showcase resources such as ‘Cheat Sheets’ and ‘Fact Sheets’, which are intended to cover key topics of the work done by the ATLAS Collaboration and the physics behind the experiment for a broad audience of all ages and levels of experience. This contribution will also present some of the efforts to make visits and available resources more inclusive and accessible to a wider and more diverse audience.

1 Introduction

One of the main responsibilities of the ATLAS Collaboration at CERN, in addition to research and development, is to bring the excitement of scientific exploration and discovery into classrooms through many science communication and educational activities. This is to ensure that students of all ages and levels can benefit from visual resources for learning particle physics. These interactions between the scientific community and students are extremely beneficial on both sides.

Various aspects of classroom engagement are discussed in this document, including the on-site and virtual visits at the ATLAS experiment, International Masterclasses, ATLAS' educational printables, including fact sheets, cheat sheets and activity books, and multiculturalism.

2 ATLAS's Classroom Engagement Activities

2.1 ATLAS On-site Visits

The on-site visit at the ATLAS Visitor Center (AVC), located at P1 on Meyrin site, is one of the most-visited guided itineraries in the CERN visit program. The visits aim to give students and teachers an overview of CERN and the ATLAS experiment, as well as their physics programs, goals, and operation. AVC was originally set up in 2011, and renovated between 2018 and 2021 [1].

In the AVC there are many installations and interfaces to support the guides on their tour, including a large full HD video wall, and three interactive touchscreens to give detailed information about the main sub-detectors. Two of these screens can be made transparent to display components and models of some sub-detectors. One exhibit of the Tile calorimeter is placed underneath a glass-floor tile. In addition, there is an ATLAS model made of LEGO pieces to illustrate the size and complexity of the detector.

The AVC is separated from the adjacent ATLAS control room by an opaque window, as shown in figure 1, which can be made transparent by a touchscreen to allow visitors to observe the work of the shift crew inside [2].

2.2 ATLAS Virtual Visits

Since its introduction in 2010, the ATLAS Virtual Visit (VV) program has given opportunities to the audiences from all over the world to explore the experiment without coming to CERN. Using a combination of video conferencing, webcasts, and video recording, the project allows for live interactions between the remote audiences and members of the collaboration. It also provides the possibility to simultaneously webcast the event to passive participants and to record the event for future viewing. People can attend two types of VV: group VV, addressed to big groups, like school and university groups, and open VV, addressed to the general public. The VV in the ATLAS cavern are streamed when possible to give audiences an exciting "behind-the-scenes" view of the technology at CERN [4].

In 2021, there were 121 visits from 46 countries, offered in 8 languages. In the first 6 months of 2023, there have been over 50 visits from 24 countries. Each visit typically hosts between 10 and 600 participants. Open visits for individuals are on a regular basis. Some visits are livestreamed to YouTube, TikTok, and other social media platforms.

2.3 International Masterclasses

The International Masterclasses (IMC) program was started in 2005 by the International Particle Physics Outreach Group (IPPOG), engaging physicists from different collaborations at different institutions to provide teaching and learning opportunities to students all over the world. In

Figure 1: The AVC with many installations and interfaces for on-site visitors [3]

2023, the program has offered a range of outreach and engagement opportunities to 13,000 high school students, gathering in more than 200 different locations from over 55 countries around the world [5].

One highlight of the IMC program is the video conference to connect students and teachers with researchers. During this activity, the students get insight into topics and methods of basic research at the fundamentals of matter and forces, and perform measurements on real ATLAS data. ATLAS physicists moderate the discussion of results by students from different schools with the use of web-based video tools, and offer out-of-the-classroom experiences such as virtual visits, conversations on different aspects of particle physics theories and experiments, and life as a physicist at the ATLAS experiment [6].

2.4 ATLAS' educational printables

A wide range of educational materials for all ages and levels of expertise (shown in figure 3) have also been offered by the ATLAS Collaboration, including 10 Fact Sheets, 5 Cheat Sheets, 2 Colouring Books, one guide for parents and teachers, and 5 Activity Sheets.

2.4.1 Fact Sheets

The Fact Sheets, available in 3 languages, with visually appealing designs, were developed with the aim of collecting facts about the ATLAS detector and the collaboration all in one place, and to provide resources for students, teachers, and guides [8].

2.4.2 Cheat Sheets

The Cheat Sheets were designed with the goal to make online scientific material - including briefings, news pieces, as well as publications from the ATLAS experiment - easier to comprehend

Figure 2: ATLAS Cavern VV host by Dr S. Goldfarb, and students F. Boreiko and M. Tiulchenko for the IMC at V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University in Ukraine (April 2023) [7]

and accessible to the general public. The language used in these sheets is simple and concise to engage the audience with an interest in learning particle physics. Each sheet covers one concept, such as ‘*Conservation Laws*’, ‘*Cross Section and Luminosity*’, ‘*Feynman Diagrams*’, ‘*Signal and Background*’, and ‘*The Standard Model*’. The cheat sheet ‘*Statistical Significance*’ is coming soon [8].

2.4.3 Colouring books and activity sheets

Colouring books aim at children between six and ten years old. ‘*The ATLAS Experiment Colouring Book*’ gives an overview of the experiment, an introduction to the Standard Model, and basic concepts of elementary particles and interactions. It was first published in 2016 and is now available in 18 languages. The second book, ‘*Particles of the Universe*’, launched in 2021 and available in 10 languages as of now, reveals more interesting facts about the roles of different elementary particles, and introduces the concepts of scale and colour charge [8].

Based on the Colouring Books, the Activity Sheets, which are available in five languages, introduce some new concepts with different levels of difficulty and allow children up to 16 years old to put into practice what they have learned with the other ATLAS educational printables. [8]

2.5 Multilingualism

ATLAS guided tours are offered in approximately 30 languages. The IMC program organized by the ATLAS Collaboration has been offered in 13 languages: English, French, German, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Norwegian, Polish, Slovak, Czech, Danish, Turkish. There are also a large number of outreach events organized in different languages by regional research groups and individual ATLAS members from different countries.

Educational materials are created by the outreach team in English, and then translated into many other languages by ATLAS members and associated volunteers. After being reviewed by

Figure 3: ATLAS' educational printables [9, 10, 11]

Figure 4: Monthly download data for: (a) Colouring books, (b) Activity Sheets, (c) Fact Sheets, (d) Cheat Sheets [12]

the members fluent in those languages, the translations have their texts and layouts reformatted before being published on the ATLAS webpage and distributed to the public.

The increase in monthly downloads of educational printables in languages other than English shown in figure 4 implies that the translations are reaching new audiences.

3 Conclusion

The ATLAS Collaboration has made great efforts to strengthen classroom engagement. The on-site visits at the AVC offer students a chance to have an overview of CERN, learn about the ATLAS detector through various interactive displays and exhibitions, and witness the operation in the control room. The virtual visits use a number of different web-based video tools to make the learning experience possible for remote audiences. The IMC, in collaboration with IPPOG, aims to bring particle physics education to students from all over the world, and give them a chance to analyse open ATLAS data and discuss results. The ATLAS Collaboration have also developed printables aiming at students of different ages and educational levels to learn particle physics in a fun way. These educational programs and printables are offered in many languages to improve multilingualism.

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